

WORD COMBINATIONS IN SECONDARY NOMINATION OF COMPUTER AND INTERNET TERMS

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Abstract. *As the term fulfills tasks such as separating clear concepts in the fields of science, technology, art, and setting boundaries between them, it keeps its terminological character only within one terminological system. The difference in the definition of the term is often explained by the fact that the term can be more than one object of science at the same time. In the Uzbek language, the derivation system of computer and Internet terms is dominated by the syntactic method of term formation. This issue is discussed in the article.*

Keywords: *denomination, secondary denomination, phrase, syntax, term, terminology, system.*

When viewed from a nomenclature perspective, Internet terms formed in the style embody meanings that are related to each other. At the level of the proposition, the structure of terms of this type allows to determine the semantic relations that make up the meaning of the arguments that perform certain semantic tasks. It shows that new names involve pre-existing ready-made lexical meanings and that the ability to create new Internet terms depends on the internal capabilities of the language, and is determined by the development of different word formation methods and models. Such Internet terms are created in an associative semantic method.

V.D. Tabanakova analyzes the term by including it in a series of words or phrases. Also, it is mentioned that the specific importance of the term should be reflected in the definitions related to the inclusion of the term in the terminological system, and the nominative function of the term by opening the connection with the scientific concept and the systematic nature of the meaning of the term should be expressed in the definition.

Syntactic-semantic disproportion of syntactic units (phrases and sentences) is a specific manifestation of form and content disproportion in the language.

The processes of turning word combinations into complex words are manifested in the lexicalization of word combinations, which is appropriate only if this term formation method is considered as one of the options for adding words rather than as an independent word formation method. If word combinations have a deep semantic meaning, they are close to phraseologisms in terms of form, but phraseological terms are characterized by the stability of their elements, but figurative transfer of meanings is not.

R.A. Budagov says about the content of word combinations: "Syntax has its own semantic category. Semantic categories are also central to syntax. Outside of content categories, syntax loses its "soul" and becomes a lifeless complex of conditional rules. The syntactic aspect of language signs is the rules of combining words in a sentence. The addition of words, the order of its parts express certain meanings, for example, by combining the words "qora" and "quti" in different order, characters of different characters and different meanings can be formed..

A.N. Kononov understands word combinations as combinations of two or more independent words that have a certain meaning and syntactically have a unique formal integrity, which can express an object, action, and sign. Syntactic-semantic disproportion of syntactic units (phrases and sentences) is a specific manifestation.

The issue of combined terms has always been one of the topical issues of terminology. The reason for this is explained by the fact that the weight of compound terms in scientific and technical terminology is much greater than other types of terms. In developed terminological systems, one-word and two-word terms are relatively active, and multi-word terms are less frequent. However, in Internet terminology, terms in the form of two or more components, in the form of word combinations, make up the largest part of the materials collected from the languages in question. Here are some examples:

Two-component terms: *Faol giperishorat, manzillar kitobi, Ada tili* etc.

Three-component terms: *muhofazaning ma'muriy choralari; shifrlangan matnga hujum* etc.

Terms with four or more components: *yaltirashga qarshi ustki qatlam; yaltirashga qarshi ustki qatlam; avtomatlashtirilgan axborot tizimlari va ularning texnologiyalarini ta'minlash vositalari* etc.

The term "*faol giperishorat*" has two components and means "a hyperlink that is selected in the web browser visiting the link". When a user clicks on a hyperlink, it means to be active during the time between clicking and releasing the mouse button.

Another two-component "*Ada tili*" term is "high-level programming language. It was developed in the late 1970s and early 1980s at the initiative of the US Department of Defense for a variety of purposes, from business applications to aeronautical systems. It's based on the Pascal language and has some serious padding and a modular structure. It is characterized by a high level of independence from operating systems, providing parallel operations and creating complex information systems. The language supports real-time parallel processing of data. The Ada language was named after August Ada Lovelace (1815-52), the world's first programmer, who participated in the development of programs for the analytical engine - the first mechanical computer.

The three-component term "*muhofazaning ma'muriy choralari*" is "security policy development and measures for its implementation." According to the requirements of documents on protection, it is necessary to carry out protection in the scope of activities (for example, keeping documents on the security policy and its implementation, choosing the location of the object, organizing the controlled (inspected) zone, protection in various carriers provides for recording, storing and circulation of documents with information, etc.

Shifrlangan matnga hujum – means "analytical attack conducted by a cryptanalyst on the basis of encrypted text only".

The four-component term "*yaltirashga qarshi ustki qatlam*" means "a special, usually multi-layer, spray on the surface of the monitor screen. It distributes the incident light and prevents glare. With an anti-glare coating, it means the image will always be sharp and bright, even in very bright rooms.

An example of a multi-component term is the term "*avtomatlashtirilgan axborot tizimlari va ularning texnologiyalarini ta'minlash vositalari*". This term is defined as "software, technical, linguistic, legal, organizational tools used or created to design and ensure the use of information

systems (computer programs; computing techniques and communication tools; dictionaries, thesauruses and classifiers; instructions and methodologies ; means rules, regulations, job instructions; drawings and their classifications, other use and observation documents).

Computer and Internet terms, regardless of whether they are in the form of words and phrases, are formed in the lexical-semantic field, build a lexical-semantic paradigm. If the model of the logical system of scientific knowledge is considered the main component of abstract knowledge, then the system of Internet terms appears as a collection of words and phrases clearly expressed in one or another natural national language, as a fragment of the lexical-semantic system of this language.

Examples of compound terms formed in the lexical semantic field are terms like " *mutlaq havola*, *mutlaq yo'l*, *mutlaq manzil*, *mutlaq ishora moslamasi*, *mutlaq xavfsizlik identifikatori* "

As we can see, the terms computer and Internet were formed through the absolute lexeme:

mutlaq ishora moslamasi (noun) ~ computer term "a mechanical or physical pointing device whose position is related to the position of the cursor on the screen. For example, if a graphics user places a pen in the upper right corner of the tablet, the cursor will move to the upper right corner of the screen or to the window on the screen associated with the pen.

mutlaq xavfsizlik identifikatori (noun)~ The term web means "a security identifier structure that contains pointers to security information associated with an object."

Abbreviations that make up a significant part of English and Uzbek language computer and Internet terminology are abbreviations formed mainly on the basis of the initial parts of the components of word combinations, and they are divided into several groups: includes abbreviations based on the capital letters of the components of the phrase. Internet term made with lexeme " *Mutlaq* " and abbreviation: *Mutlaq URL manzil (internet)* – the address of a page or other resource on the Internet. The content of an absolute URL consists of a protocol such as "http", a network location, and an additional path and file name. For example, <http://www.gov.uz/> means absolute URL address.

Thus, the terms related to all fields have a nominative function, and in the process of naming, the terms related to the Internet serve to express abstract and concrete concepts, animate and inanimate objects, countable and uncountable objects. It can be said that there is a need to nominate new Internet concepts for Uzbekistan, which, in turn, indicates that it is not reflected in the lexical system of the Uzbek language. Computer and Internet terms can be classified into three groups: compound words, compound words, double words. The creation of new types of electronic tools, software, and services in computer technologies and the Internet over time creates the need to name them. The essence of nomination does not represent a name through a linguistic sign, but interprets a certain abstraction as the final result of human cognitive activity.

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